

L. I. Donets, A. V. Sergeeva

Strategic partnership of entrepreneurial ecosystems in the conditions of digitalization of the economy

KEYWORDS

strategic partnership,
 entrepreneurial ecosystem,
 digitalization of the economy,
 innovative development,
 entrepreneurial structures

Word Cloud Generated by:
<https://wordcloud.pythonanywhere.com/>

ABSTRACT

Introduction. Strategic partnership in entrepreneurial ecosystems is becoming a key element of success in digitalization environment. It provides both innovative development and sustainable competitiveness in a rapidly changing economic environment.

The article aims to scientifically and methodologically substantiate the ecosystem approach to strategic partnership of entrepreneurial structures (at the theoretical level) and to develop a model of such approach to strategic partnership of entrepreneurial structures in conditions of digitalized economy (at the methodological level).

Materials and methods. The materials were scientific articles, books, and reports on strategic partnerships, ecosystems, and the digital economy.

Research results. The components considered informing ecosystem-based strategic partnerships of entrepreneurial structures determine the output descriptors for further partnership development, including ecosystem product, ecosystem values of partners, and ecosystem synergy. Strategic alliances based on the ecosystem approach are becoming increasingly popular in the following sectors and areas of entrepreneurial activity: e-commerce, e-grocery, online educational services, food and ready-to-eat food delivery services, cell phone services, financial and banking services, cloud technologies, entertainment, payment for public services, transportation and logistics services, tourism industry, government services, etc.

Conclusion. Based on the above, the authors identified the following as priority areas for the development of ecosystem strategic partnership: rapid growth of e-commerce based on hybrid formats of partnership interaction of offline and online trade in goods and services, development of mobile applications for online sales, active introduction of e-commerce elements in social networks, personalization of sales processes, etc.; growing competition of digital ecosystems in finance, ordering, delivery, shopping, entertainment, mobile services, etc.; growing competition for digital ecosystems in e-commerce.

FOR CITATION

Donets, L. I., & Sergeeva, A. V. (2023). Strategic partnership of entrepreneurial ecosystems in the conditions of digitalization of the economy. *Economic consultant*, (3), 42–52. <https://doi.org/10.46224/ecoc.2023.3.4>

INTRODUCTION

This topic is relevant because, in the digital age, companies must constantly adapt to rapidly changing market conditions. Strategic partnerships help pool resources, expertise, and knowledge, allowing for faster development and implementation of innovative solutions.

Partnerships foster the development of sustainable business models. For example, SMEs can collaborate with large corporations to access new markets and technologies, facilitating their growth and development.

Digitalization enables sharing data that can be used to analyze consumer behavior. Partnerships in ecosystems help optimize processes and offer more personalized services and products.

Companies are forced to look for partners outside their regions in a competitive global economy. This opens up new opportunities for growth and expansion and helps share expertise.

At times, companies lack sufficient resources to implement complex projects. Partnerships allow sharing costs and risks, which is especially important in a highly uncertain environment.

Thus, strategic partnerships in entrepreneurial ecosystems are key to success in a digitized environment. They provide innovative development and sustainable competitiveness in a rapidly changing economic climate.

The article aims to scientifically and methodologically substantiate the ecosystem approach to strategic partnership of entrepreneurial structures (at the theoretical level) and to develop a model of such approach to strategic partnership of entrepreneurial structures in conditions of digitalized economy (at the methodological level).

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The materials were scientific articles, books, and reports on strategic partnerships, ecosystems, and the digital economy, particularly those published in the Review of Managerial Science, Eurasian Business Review, The Journal of Technology Transfer, Small Business Economics, SN Business & Economics, International Entrepreneurship and Management Journal, Review of Managerial Science, Journal of Management, Harvard Business Review, and others.

LITERATURE REVIEW

R. B. Bouncken and S. Kraus write that interrelated actors (governments, private sector, society, universities, entrepreneurs, and others) create an ecosystem, i.e., a social and economic environment for innovative and entrepreneurial endeavors. The key idea is that firms base their business models on shared resources, network externalities, knowledge spillovers, local funds, and government support [1].

S. Scott conceptualizes entrepreneurial ecosystems as networks with symbiotic relationships. According to the authors, insufficient attention is paid to the behavioral and governance factors that underlie how the qualitative interactions making up an entrepreneurial ecosystem evolve and change over time [2].

X. Han writes that, first, strategic alliances play a significant role in the entrepreneurial ecosystem (EE) given the advantage of accessing valuable and complementary external resources that firms do not yet possess; second, strategic alliances as elements of the external accumulation sub-ecosystem of the entrepreneurial ecosystem are interdependent and co-evolve with the internal accumulation sub-ecosystem [3].

M. H. Bala Subrahmanya notes that despite the growth of ecosystems, the success rate of high-tech startups did not increase during this period. In the author's opinion, this highlights the critical importance of "competitiveness of high-tech startups" and the need to study the determinants of competitiveness in entrepreneurial ecosystems. The author also points out that the entrepreneurial ecosystem for high-tech startups is invariably regional, as regions differ in politics, culture, concentration of firms, educational institutions, markets, human resources, and availability of finance, among others [4].

M. F. Riaz et al. assess the moderating effect of institutional transparency on the relationship between the entrepreneurial ecosystem and startups. According to the authors, increasing financial and economic openness in urban planning constrains the formation of new businesses in a municipality, while municipalities where public procurement is relatively transparent attract more startups [5].

J. Zhang believes that relatively little is known about how and to what extent digital technologies affect a country's entrepreneurial activities. Based on the entrepreneurial ecosystem concept, the authors developed a conceptual model to explain the impact of digital technologies on national entrepreneurship and the interactions between digital technologies and other ecosystem elements [6].

D. Prokop and P. Thompson write that entrepreneurial ecosystems characterized by openness to various actors create more firms. The authors examine 81 entrepreneurial ecosystems of the UK universities and recognize the relationship between an ecosystem's openness to various actors and its entrepreneurial efficiency [7].

According to A. F. Bate, effectiveness of entrepreneurial activity is determined by the quality of entrepreneurs and the entrepreneurial ecosystem. The authors' study compares the entrepreneurial ecosystems of BRICS countries, particularly South Africa, Brazil, and India. According to the authors, South Africa (57th out of 140 as of 2018) is among the low-performing countries regarding startup skills, networking, technology absorption, human capital, and risk capital [8].

A. Alaassar et al. analyze the role of EE in creating an enabling environment for productive entrepreneurship. The authors examine how the interactions of ecosystem actors affect new ventures in financial technology (fintech) EE in Singapore [9].

S. Moggi et al. propose a theoretical framework for a thriving entrepreneurial ecosystem. Thriving is a new entrepreneurial approach that introduces an overarching view in which sustainability is a "path to follow" rather than a goal to be achieved. The authors support that organizations can collaborate in a thriving entrepreneurial ecosystem as a unique entity that respects nature, contributing to the economic viability of both firms and territories by improving the quality of life and caring for natural resources and local communities [10].

Thus, studying the theoretical foundations of cooperation, network governance, and platform economics is relevant. Ecosystem partnerships allow entrepreneurs to share resources, knowledge, and technology, promoting innovation.

Researching this topic can use quantitative and qualitative methods. This includes analyzing statistical data on company interactions and conducting interviews with key players in the ecosystem.

The research results can be helpful for companies seeking to create effective ecosystems and government agencies developing policies to support entrepreneurship in digitalization.

Analyzing successful examples of strategic partnerships in different sectors, such as finance, technology, or healthcare, allows us to identify best practices and mistakes, further enriching scientific knowledge.

With the rapid digitalization of the economy, software solutions such as cloud technology, big data, and artificial intelligence are beginning to play a key role in business; this creates a need for strategic partnerships to ensure competitiveness and sustainable growth.

RESEARCH FINDINGS

In today's digital world, business structures can form and develop ecosystem strategic partnerships within five types of ecosystems (platforms, innovation, interests, commerce, and things), which were proposed by representatives of the consulting company Gartner [11]. Table 1 presents a comparative analysis of these types, showing that every kind of ecosystem strategic partnership has its own focus and target vector.

Table 1

Comparative analysis of types of ecosystem strategic partnerships of entrepreneurial structures

No.	Type of ESP	Focus of partnerships	Target vector of ESP	Examples of ESPs
1	Platform ecosystem	Software platform	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> growth (expansion) of the number of services and services within the platform; increase in complementarity of the aggregate product 	Apple, Google, Facebook, Dropbox, Airbnb, Uber, General Electric
2	Innovation ecosystem	Open Innovation concept	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> accelerated new products and services development; reduced research costs; reduced time-to-market for new products and services 	P&G Connect and Develop, Kraft Foods, GE Open Innovation, Samsung, Riversimple
3	Commerce Ecosystem	Supply Chain	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> optimized relationships between participants; coordination of participants to achieve individual or collective efficiencies in the IT marketplace, logistics supply chains 	IT marketplace, logistics supply chains
4	Interest ecosystem	Communities of interest	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> promotion of own products and services; development of innovations 	Reddit, Renren, Edmodo, Cyworld
5	Things ecosystem	Internet of Things (IoT)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> real-time access to information about product and service usage; access to big data, Industrial Internet, logistics supply chains, and healthcare 	Industrial Internet, logistics supply chains, and healthcare

Systematized, summarized, and supplemented by the authors per source [12]

The structural framework of the ecosystem strategic partnership of entrepreneurial structures is formed by its participants – partner agents and the roles they fulfill. The authors propose to distinguish four groups of ESP agents:

- partners-owners – owners of the core business who manage the ecosystem;
- partners-organizers-providers – entrepreneurial structures that organize the whole process of building the ecosystem, interact with contractors, allow others to participate in the ecosystem, sell products and services through a specific platform, carry out their functioning;

- partners-modular producers – entrepreneurial structures that contribute to the development of the ecosystem by adding their goods and services to the base product and participating in the creation of the aggregate product;
- consumer partners – customers (people), businesses, and other entities that benefit from participation in the ecosystem and consume the ecosystem product.

Provided that the boundaries between ecosystem strategic partnership participants are blurred, they can simultaneously organize, use, and consume ecosystem services and participate in multiple ecosystems. An ecosystem strategic partnership's technical and technological component is a digital platform and infrastructure through which technological processes are implemented and supported. The ecosystem's product base consists of partner goods and services (complementary products) that complement and synchronize the basic product, create its complementarity and form the ecosystem product. The functionality of the digital platform is essential in each ecosystem, which allows the other components to work effectively and improve their goods and services. The ecosystem strategic partnership functionality forms the basis for further development of the ecosystem and its product, realizing the following functions:

- developing the ecosystem product concept and overseeing the implementation of its elements or as a whole;
- developing a comprehensive ecosystem development strategy;
- forming tasks and targets for ecosystem development;
- forming procedures and rules for building partnership relations in the ecosystem and their development;
- generating management impacts of each partner in the ecosystem;
- building communication mechanisms between ESP agents;
- forming a familiar environment and interaction with other ecosystems, firms, government, society;
- developing projects for innovative development of goods and services within the ecosystem product;
- selecting new ESP partner agents.
- managing the level of ecosystem risk, etc.

The development of an ecosystem strategic partnership depends on the chosen strategy for forming and developing entrepreneurial structures within digital ecosystems, the variability of which is presented in Table 2.

The components considered informing ecosystem strategic partnerships of entrepreneurial structures determine the output descriptors for the further development of partnerships, which include an ecosystem product, ecosystem values of partners, and ecosystem synergy.

Each participant in an ecosystem strategic partnership derives its value from partnering within the ecosystem. Owner partners reduce resource costs for service delivery, gain the ability to diversify and develop the underlying product, and expand sites by entering other industries and markets. Organizer partners increase their customer base through their digital technologies and services. Partner-modular producers get access to narrow segments of consumers who have an established need, additional digital services for their work, opportunities for rapid growth, diversification and risk reduction, ability to study information on the interaction of market participants and make decisions to optimize these interactions, ability to provide a more complete service to the consumer, drastically reduce costs for marketing and promotion of their products and services, etc. Partner-consumers receive an ecosystem (aggregate) product which results from the interaction between ecosystem agents in goods, services, and works united by a single umbrella brand.

Table 2

Variability of strategies to form and develop ESP of entrepreneurial structures

No.	Formation strategy	Key provisions	Ways of developing ESP
1	Customer orientation strategy	Attracting traffic (customer orders), transferring them to implementing partners, and coordinating work on orders	Equal involvement of partner resources and competencies
2	Strategy focusing on implementing partners.	Attracting implementing partners and organizing their interaction with clients within the framework of the platform	
3	Strategy of the key implementing partner	Creation of its partner platform and the gradual involvement of other implementing partners in it, as the number of orders increases	Predominance of its resources and competencies, with the involvement of partners
4	Strategy of serving the market for its product	Attracting partners to serve the market, which is formed around its own (basic) product	

Systematized, generalized, and supplemented by the authors according to the sources [13; 14]

The values of the partners as a whole form the ecosystem synergy of the strategic partnership, which is manifested in exceeding the effectiveness of the joint work of agents within the ecosystem over the effectiveness of their work individually. Strategic partnerships based on an ecosystem approach are becoming increasingly popular in such industries and business areas as e-commerce, e-grocery, online educational services, food and ready-to-eat delivery services, mobile communication services, financial and banking services, cloud technologies, entertainment, payment for public services, transport and logistics services, tourism industry, government services, etc.

Participation in the digital ecosystem is a necessary stage in developing entrepreneurial structures. Among the most well-known global companies using an ecosystem approach in strategic partnerships are the following: Apple, Google, Microsoft, Facebook, Amazon, Alibaba,

Tencent, Uber, Airbnb, Samsung, Dropbox, General Electric, P&G Connect and Develop, Kraft Foods, Riversimple, Edmodo, etc. [15].

DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

As digitalization permeates every business area, ecosystems are essential for creating sustainable competitive advantages. Companies are increasingly joining in ecosystems to share resources and knowledge. Partnerships within ecosystems allow implementing innovative ideas faster and adapting to changes in the market [16]; this is especially important in a rapidly changing digital environment.

A strategic partnership opens up access to new markets and consumer segments. Companies can expand their presence through joint initiatives which are critical for growth.

Partnerships allow companies to integrate different technologies, improving the quality of products and services. For instance, collaborative platform development can lead to more efficient business processes and a better user experience.

Partner teams working on sustainable and socially responsible projects will be able to effectively address modern challenges such as climate change and social justice.

Academic institutions' research in strategic partnership offers innovative approaches that can help properly adjust ecosystems [17]; this enriches practice and substantiates theory.

Using data analytics and AI to improve partnership strategies [18]; these technologies can help understand which partners will bring the most value.

Based on the above, the authors identified the following as priority areas for the development of ecosystem strategic partnership:

- rapid development of e-commerce based on hybrid formats of partnership between offline and online trade in goods and services, development of mobile applications for online sales, active introduction of e-commerce elements into social networks, personalization of sales processes, etc.
- increased competition of digital ecosystems in finance, orders, delivery, shopping, entertainment, mobility, and healthcare;
- an increase in the trend of investments in the so-called Tech sectors, for example, FoodTech, EdTech, HealthTech, MediaTech, etc., as well as in big data analysis systems, cloud technologies, remote communications, cybersecurity, electronic document management, virtual network protection (VPN), self-driving cars, 5G, Internet of Things (IoT) to integrate them into ecosystems;
- intensive increase in the structural elements of existing digital ecosystems by blurring the boundaries between sectors and industries of the economy, between competitors, and their active convergence;

- active development of a model of equal strategic partnership within digital ecosystems in the B2C (business-consumer) services segment by partner companies with a developed technological platform, well-integrated services, and a seamless user experience;
- introduction of government mechanisms for regulating and supporting digital ecosystems.

REFERENCES

1. Bouncken, R. B., Kraus, S. (2022). Entrepreneurial ecosystems in an interconnected world: emergence, governance and digitalization. *Review of Managerial Science*, 16, 1–14. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11846-021-00444-1>
2. Scott, S., Hughes, M., & Ribeiro-Soriano, D. (2022). Towards a network-based view of effective entrepreneurial ecosystems. *Review of Managerial Science*, 16, 157–187. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11846-021-00440-5>
3. Han, X. (2022). The Role of Strategic Alliances in Developing the Entrepreneurial Ecosystem of ICV Industry: The Case of NIO Inc.. In: *Pechlaner, H., Thees, H., Manske-Wang, W. (eds) The Clash of Entrepreneurial Cultures?. FGF Studies in Small Business and Entrepreneurship*. Springer, Cham. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-97050-5_11
4. Bala Subrahmanya, M. H. (2022). Competitiveness of High-Tech Start-Ups and Entrepreneurial Ecosystems: An Overview. *JGBC*, 17, 1–10. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s42943-022-00056-w>
5. Riaz, M. F., Leitro, J., & Cantner, U. (2022). Measuring the efficiency of an entrepreneurial ecosystem at municipality level: does institutional transparency play a moderating role?. *Eurasian Business Review*, 12, 151–176. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s40821-021-00194-w>
6. Zhang, J., van Gorp, D., & Kievit, H. (2023). Digital technology and national entrepreneurship: An ecosystem perspective. *The Journal of Technology Transfer*, 48, 1077–1105. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10961-022-09934-0>
7. Prokop, D., Thompson, P. (2023). Defining networks in entrepreneurial ecosystems: the openness of ecosystems. *Small Business Economics*, 61, 517–538. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11187-022-00710-w>
8. Bate, A. F. (2021). A comparative analysis on the entrepreneurial ecosystem of BRICS club countries: practical emphasis on South Africa. *SN Business & Economics*, 1, 121. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s43546-021-00120-2>
9. Alaassar, A., Mention, AL., & Aas, T. H. (2022). Ecosystem dynamics: exploring the interplay within fintech entrepreneurial ecosystems. *Small Business Economics*, 58, 2157–2182. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11187-021-00505-5>
10. Moggi, S., Pierce, P. & Bernardi, N. (2022). From sustainability to thriving: A novel framework for entrepreneurial ecosystems. *International Entrepreneurship and*

- Management Journal*, 18, 829–853. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11365-021-00787-x>
- 11.5 Strategies for Building Business Ecosystems. Available at: <https://denreymer.com/digital-ecosystem> (accessed 12 June 2022)
 12. Best examples of digital ecosystems and superapps. Available at: <https://vc.ru/services/181804-luchshie-primery-cifrovyyh-ekosistem-i-superappov> (accessed 12 June 2022)
 13. Rayanov, R. What is a platform business, creating a marketplace platform for the industry. Platform business model. Available at: <https://falconspace.ru/blog/chto-takoe-platformenny-biznes--sozdanie-platformy-marketpleysa-dlya-otrasli--biznes-model-platforma> (accessed 12 June 2022)
 14. What is the digital economy? Trends, competencies, measurement: XX Apr. International Scientific Conf. on the Problems of Development of Economy and Society, Moscow, 9-12 Apr. 2019 / G. I. Abdrakhmanova, K. O. Vishnevsky, L. M. Gokhberg et al. ; scientific ed. L. M. Gokhberg ; National Research University Higher School of Economics. Moscow, Higher School of Economics, 2019. 82 p.
 15. Makarkin N. P., Gorina A. P., Alferina A. P., & Korneeva N. V. (2020). Digitalization of business in pandemic conditions. *Bulletin of the Altai Academy of Economics and Law*, 11, 80–85.
 16. Lall, S. A., Chen, L. W., & Mason, D. P. (2023). Digital platforms and entrepreneurial support: a field experiment in online mentoring. *Small Business Economics*, 61, 631–654. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11187-022-00704-8>
 17. Cloutier, L., & Messeghem, K. (2022). Whirlwind model of entrepreneurial ecosystem path dependence. *Small Business Economics*, 59, 611–625. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11187-021-00553-x>
 18. Song, Y., Escobar, O., & Arzubiaga, U. et al. (2022). The digital transformation of a traditional market into an entrepreneurial ecosystem. *Review of Managerial Science*, 16, 65–88. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11846-020-00438-5>
 19. Adner R. (2017). Ecosystem as Structure: An Actionable Construct for Strategy. *Journal of Management*, 43 (1), 39–58.
 20. Alstynne M., Parker G., & Choudary S. (2016). Pipelines, Platforms, and the New Rules of Strategy. *Harvard Business Review*, 54–60. Available at: <https://hbr.org/2016/04/pipelines-platforms-and-the-new-rules-of-strategy> (accessed 12 June 2022).
 21. Ceccagnoli M., Forman C., Huang P., & Wu D. J. (2012). Co-creation of Value in a Platform Ecosystem: The case of enterprise software. *MIS Quarterly*, 36 (1), 263–290.
 22. Adner, Ron. (2016). Ecosystem as Structure: An Actionable Construct for Strategy. *Journal of Management*, 43 (1), 39–58. DOI: 10.1177/0149206316678451.
 23. Gawer, A. (2014). Bridging Differing Perspectives on Technological Platforms: Toward an Integrative Framework. *Research Policy*, 43 (7), 1239–1249.

